

A STUDY ON LINKEDIN MARKETING BY INTEGRATING WITH EMAIL MARKETING IN INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY BASED B2B INDUSTRY

SURJADEEP DUTTA¹ and ARIVAZHAGAN.R^{2*}

¹Research Scholar and ²Associate professor

^{1,2}College of Management, SRM Institute of Science and Technology, Kattankulathur.

*Corresponding author Email: arivazhr@srmist.edu.in

Abstract:

The Trend of social media marketing is increasing a lot. During covid-19 pandemic the entire concept of offline promotion got stopped and digital marketing trend got increased. Digital marketing is the promotion of the products and services through online and helps in the business development and growth by connecting with the potential clients. Social media marketing and content marketing plays a great role in B2B Business. LinkedIn Marketing is considered to be one of the most powerful tools for B2B business. Though LinkedIn marketing considered as one of the dominant social media tools in broader perspective, it was little dilemma that what specific LinkedIn factors will influence the marketers to use them predominantly for the purpose of marketing. Hence this research was conducted with the objective of identifying those factors. Structured questionnaire was prepared by using demographic variables and other LinkedIn specific variables identified from the literatures. The data was collected from 137 respondents who worked in IT based B2B companies based on convenience sampling method. Data was collected through online survey method and interview method. Collected data was analyzed and results were declared. This research concludes that demographic factors like age and occupation are having strong influence on the awareness of LinkedIn marketing. Further, this research reveals that marketing strategy plays a major role followed by belief of respondents.

Keywords: Content Marketing, Digital Marketing, Email Marketing, LinkedIn Marketing, Social Media Marketing.

INTRODUCTION:

LinkedIn Marketing is the most powerful marketing tool in Digital Marketing for Lead Generation in B2B Business. Previously offline marketing was there. People were less aware of the online marketing. So they used to work in field for promoting the business using printed banners and posters and they used to call the clients for the business deal. Now day's online marketing brought a great change in the market. In 2021, mostly all the marketers use social media marketing for the brand identity of their business. The digital marketing help the company people to promote their products online and to generate leads. Now the people no need to go to anywhere for the promotions of their products .The digital marketing is also very cost effective and time saving method than the offline promotion of the B2B Business. Now more than millions of people use social media. So all are connected with each other. Here In this project we talk about how LinkedIn marketing is a powerful social media business tool for B2B marketing.

In LinkedIn, marketers can design their company's page and portfolio. It is a great decision for the marketers to set up the business connections through LinkedIn because it not only helps in

Brand Identity But also helps to deal with right customers at right place and at right time. LinkedIn company pages are free to build-up. No charges are required to build the company's business page in LinkedIn. Marketers can able to post the posters with attractive content.

LinkedIn Marketing helps the Marketers to get enough information about their potential customers and their business for the Lead Generation. Here there is a Research Gap. Many tele callers of every sector get Leads but they are not getting the proper Leads for Sales Conversion. They are using all social media channels for the Lead Generation. Many Peoples are enquiring but most of Sales people or tele callers are lagging behind because they don't get any proper Data for B2B sales. There is a difference between B2B sales and B2C sales. For B2C Sales every social media Channels are great for lead generation and lead conversion but for B2B sales it has been noticed that LinkedIn marketing plays a very important and vital Role than Facebook Marketing and Instagram marketing. InB2C (Business to Consumer) marketing the marketers directly deals with the target customers or individual or group of customers of the particular products or services he is dealing with.

The products may be essential for all the customers like edu-tech sectors and banking Industries all are doing B2C marketing. B2B business is a type of ecommerce business which interchanges the products and services between companies like software industries, Flipkart, Amazon all conducts B2B marketing. But here we can notice that if we interconnect LinkedIn Business Marketing with Telemarketing then in particular B2B industries there will be a great change. Proper lead generation will happen using the LinkedIn business Marketing and those leads the tele-callers can use for telemarketing with their respective contact details. As we know for telemarketing proper details of the business are required and they should connect with a genuine person of the company so LinkedIn Marketing plays a great role.

Enough Researches have been done on social media marketing but no one noticed that LinkedIn is powerful tool for tele-callers or marketers to get genuine leads as per requirements and helps to convert the leads. Marketers should remember that there are many decision makers available on the LinkedIn. The relationship they will make on the LinkedIn by accept and follow of the request. The marketers should post regularly with the contents and share the right content with their potential clients in LinkedIn to have a strong collaboration so that it will be easy for the telemarketing people while have a interaction over phone so that they can convert the leads easily. Marketers should always shares updates and opinions and also they should interact with the client and quick response should be given on the client's question for the positive impact. The marketers should also focus on the video content of the business for the showcase so that the clients should get impressed on the content.

Tele-callers may follow the digital marketing team so that there will be no miscommunication. After generation of leads through the LinkedIn the digital marketer should pass all the contact information to the tele-callers or sales executive of the respective company. Here comes another point that if the client provides email id then what tele-caller will do? The tele-caller should go for another Lead and it is the duty of the digital marketing executive to send a proposal through email to their client or to perform email marketing So that customer can share contact information which the tele-callers can use for lead conversion

LITERATURE REVIEW:

In a study of 'A critical review of Digital Marketing' by M.Bala (2018) stated that they experienced a radical change in India towards digitalization. Here the consumer are looking and searching more on internet to find the best deal form the sellers around India as compared to traditional or conventional methods. Here they Noticed that Digital Marketing SEO, SEM, Content Marketing, e-mail marketing, display advertising are becoming more and more common in our advancing technology. As per M.Bala (2018) it is demonstrated that we all are connected through Whatsapp and Facebook and the increasing use of social media is creating new opportunities for digital marketers to attract the customers through digital platform. Awareness of consumer's motives is important because it provides a deeper understanding of what influences users to create content about a brand or store.

From the study 'setting the future of digital and social media marketing research: Perspectives and research propositions' by Yogesh. K.Dwivedi mentioned that the use of Social Media Marketing and Internet Have changed the Consumer Behaviour and the various ways by which the company can perform their business .Social Media Marketing is cost effective and also improved the Business Opportunities and helps in the growth of sales. Here the speaker strongly focussed on Digital Content Management , mobile marketing , B2B Marketing but he didn't mentioned About LinkedIn Marketing Usefulness in B2B Marketing.

From the study 'Social Media Marketing : Strategies and Its Impact' by Vivek Bajpai (2012) he mentioned that Social Media helps in connecting themselves with social networking sites through which now people can stay far and can remain connected . He only Focused on Facebook and explained Facebook creates a great connection between products and individuals which leads to large advertising agency. He also mentioned that other social media platforms like blogs create a platform to post comment on any event which needs to be publicized also can be utilized as a promotional technique for customer's adoption as well as for promotions.

LinkedIn Marketing – Deficiency in B2B Business

LinkedIn Marketing helps the B2B business to run efficiently. Most of the start-up of different sectors fails to use this Strategy. They are using LinkedIn Marketing to Post Job Opportunities not for the Lead Generation Purpose. The Digital Marketing Strategist use Facebook, Instagram and Blogging Platform to Generate Leads and Sales Revenue. If the digital marketing strategist Use the LinkedIn platform they will get leads as per their exact requirement. The leads they will get here they can easily connect those leads with the Telemarketing Executive who will convert those deal by phone or by follow up. It is the work of the digital marketing strategist who will do a follow up through Email. The Content marketing and Email proposal should be more impressive.

From the study of 'Email Marketing : Advantages , Disadvantages and Improving Techniques' by E.Fariborzi (2012) the author mentioned that email marketing helps for communication and also provides fund-raising messages by targeting the audience .E.Fariborzi (2012) mentioned that every E-mail sent to a potential Customer or current customer is known as email marketing.

In the Literature E.Fariborzi (2012) mentioned that the content should be good and valuable content and Email Subject line to be made to make the potential customers more engaging . Here Researcher can see that Email Marketing and Content Marketing are closely interconnected with each other because for proper email marketing we need good content.

From the Literature of E.Fariborzi (2012) researcher can see that for Email Marketing the content is very much Important. In the article titled “Organization’s use of LinkedIn: An analysis of non-profits, large corporations and small businesses” by Lisa Witzig (2012) they mentioned that every business have a LinkedIn business page. They also mentioned that LinkedIn provides the organization a good opportunity to connect on a more quality organization to better understand and target the audience. Lisa Witzig mentioned that company digital marketers use this tool to enhance their goal.

From the statement of Lisa Witzig(2012) research can say that LinkedIn marketing in large and small corporations have a good opportunity to connect with quality audience and for better deals. From the study of “Internet Marketing or Modern Advertising! How? Why?” by Masoud Nosrati (2013) mentioned how internet marketing or digital marketing can generate leads and drive direct sales from website and emails.

From the Study “Email Marketing in the era of the empowered consumer by Mari Hartemo (2016) in Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing” it is observed that Email permits a functioning, intuitive and customized correspondence satisfying the inclinations of an enabled buyer. Email promoting can be utilized to enable buyers by sending messages in view of consent, by making customers dynamic members in the correspondence cycle and by making messages applicable for the beneficiaries. Notwithstanding, current email showcasing techniques should be refreshed to get the most extreme advantage out of the channel.

Interconnection between the LinkedIn Marketing, Email Marketing, Content Marketing, Lead /Revenue Generation

Here will show the how LinkedIn Marketing is interconnected with the other Email Marketing, Content Marketing, telemarketing executive results in leads and revenue generation. It has been observed that LinkedIn Marketing plays a very important role in B2B business.

Attractive and impressive content engages more clients in various social media platforms. Telemarketing executive should have proper coordination with the digital marketing strategist for lead generation and business development and they should avoid discrepancies. After lead gets generated then immediate the digital marketer needs to send the proposal of the attractive content to the clients so that the client’s get good knowledge about the products and services which will be a great interaction between telemarketing executive and clients in B2B business.

Dr.Chitra.K (2016) stated that the total number of social media users has been rising as a result of various developments, including better broadband accessibility, better software tools, and the creation of more potent computers and mobile devices; social developments, including rising computer and software affordability; and growing commercial interest in social media sites. Recognizing these technological advances, the majority of the organisations began to

reinvent themselves, putting an emphasis on developing interactive relationships with customers through participation in various social media channels. To engage their customers, businesses use a variety of social media marketing techniques. A social media marketing strategy (SMMS) is a plan of action that describes how a business or organisation plans to use the resources and capabilities of social media to satisfy its marketing goals and the needs of its target market.

Email Marketing: Powerful Tool to engage customers

Pantea Carmen (2010) stated that the email is a useful marketing tool for communicating brief, straightforward messages that urge the receiver to take action. Typically, businesses create email marketing campaigns to draw in new clients, stimulate repeat business from current clients, reward customer loyalty, and announce or remind clients about special deals or occasions. An email marketing campaign needs more responses from the target audience in order to be effective.

Samsudeen Sabraz Nawaz (2020) stated that one of the most common marketing strategies utilised by businesses, particularly through social media and email marketing, is digital marketing. Social media and email marketing have been found to be highly effective in fostering customer engagement, which is a factor that affects the frequency of customers' purchase intentions, in addition to being simple to use and robust. In general, digital marketing technologies allow businesses to promote their goods easily and cultivate client relationships for less money, which increases sales volume.

SS Veleva (2019) stated that the process of transforming a business into a digital one includes digital marketing. It integrates brand-new information and communication technology-based marketing strategies. Because of this, its practical application is a requirement for the growth of the company in the current market conditions.

Alaka Samantaray (2020) stated nowadays, internet marketing plays a significant role in e-commerce and includes a variety of methods for promoting the company, including e-mail marketing, digital marketing, social networking sites, affiliate marketing, and more. Given that email marketing is one of the most effective communication channels, the paper's goal is to demonstrate its usefulness. Basic email marketing analytics like arrival time, open time, and user clicking are only discussed in a small fraction of the essay. At the end of the piece are suggestions and tips for writing uplifting emails. The eye tracking device is also used to analyse mailbox viewing patterns among Internet users. The manner that businesses conduct their business is altered by commerce. The Iranian government has developed a number of strategies to enhance e-commerce activity because it understands how important it is to contribute to the country's economic growth through the internet. Paper intends to make it possible for both public and private businesses to use e-commerce as a tool to boost competition in international marketplaces. One of the e-commerce methods is email marketing. E-mail marketing is a type of direct marketing that involves sending out emails to recipients in order to advertise or raise money. Mehedi Hasan (2021) stated that Social media's rising popularity has given marketers a better platform to interact with consumers. However, little study has been done to examine

the effects of social media marketing from the standpoint of branding. Furthermore, only a few studies on global branding have looked into how consumer-brand interactions are impacted by a brand's local or global positioning.

Simona Vinerean (2021) stated that customer engagement has become an essential part of social media marketing tactics, sparking academics' and marketers' intense interest. Severina Cartwright (2021) stated that social networking is evolving into a useful tool for businesses that conduct business with other businesses (B2B). The majority of study to date has been concentrated on the tactical use of social media platforms, that is, on detailing specific tools to implement a plan, so there is a lack of a thorough strategic overview of social media research in B2B.

Problem statement considered for this study:

Review of literatures were clearly states that LinkedIn will help the organizations and specifically marketers in various ways such as lead generation, customer services, customer relationship management, etc. Whereas, what factors from the perspective of LinkedIn will influence the marketers to use them has not been addressed clearly. Hence this aspect has been considered as problem statement for this research work and objectives were formulated accordingly.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES:

From the review of literatures and its related problem statement, following objectives were finalized to undertake this study.

- To understand the demographic profiles of the respondents those who are using LinkedIn marketing and its relationship with awareness and usage of the same
- To identify the factors influencing for the LinkedIn marketing with respect to IT based B2B industries

Research Methodology:

The entire research was conducted based on descriptive method of research design. The major aim of the research is to help all the B2B sectors to run their business using LinkedIn. Scope of the study was restricted within IT based B2B companies located in Chennai region. Further this study has been confined within the companies those who are using social media as their one of the marketing tool. Structured questionnaire was prepared by using demographic variables and other LinkedIn specific variables identified from the literatures. The data was collected from 137 respondents who worked in IT based B2B companies based on convenience Sampling method. Data was collected through online survey method and interview method.

DATA ANALYSIS

After collecting the data it was processed through elimination of incomplete and missed data, coded and tabulated in the MS-excel sheet initially. Then all those data were transferred to SPSS software and ensured no missed data. Data reliability was checked and confirmed its

consistency since the Cronbach's alpha value of the variables was 0.779 and hence further analyses carried out by using suitable statistical tools.

Demography profiles of the respondents:

Frequency analysis was carried out to understand the respondents' status in terms of their demography details.

Sl. No.	Demography factor	Specific highlighting criteria	% of response
1	Age	Between 21 and 30 years	68%
2	Marital status	Unmarried	66%
3	Annual income	Between 1 and 2.4 lakhs	44%
4	Annual income	Between 2.5 and 5 lakhs	25%
5.	Occupation	Private Employee	51%
6.	Industrial Sector	IT Industry	49%

This study includes maximum (68%) numbers of respondents from the age group of 19 to 30 years. Around two third (66%) of respondents in this study was unmarried. This study was conducted with the maximum (69%) number of respondents who earning their annual income less than 5 lakhs. This study includes maximum (51%) of the employees work in private sector. Around (49%) of the respondent are from education industries. The study includes maximum of (74%) of the respondents who are aware of the LinkedIn Marketing. Around (74%) of the total respondents thinks LinkedIn as a strong business tool for B2B Business. Around (40%) of the total respondents are not aware of the organisation's LinkedIn marketing strategy. The study was conducted with maximum (53%) of the respondents who answered their company use LinkedIn Marketing for Product Branding, (50%) of maximum respondents answered that their company use LinkedIn Marketing for Job Posting. Around (75%) of the total respondents think that organisation should focus in LinkedIn Marketing for Lead Generation in B2B Business. Around (43%) of the respondents mentioned that organisation's sales team closes the Deal coming from LinkedIn. The study includes maximum of (49%) of the respondents who mentioned that their company use LinkedIn Marketing and Email Marketing both for Lead Generations and Sales Closure. Around (54%) of the total respondents believe that LinkedIn and Email Marketing are best for B2B lead generation and also LinkedIn and email are the convenient tool to have a strong customer relationship.

This study indicates maximum (46%) of the respondents use LinkedIn tool weekly. Around (56%) of the respondents have 50+ connections in LinkedIn. The Study includes maximum (81%) of the respondents who have never posted any blogs in LinkedIn. Around (92%) of the total respondents doesn't pay for using LinkedIn. The study includes maximum (36%) of the respondents who are not aware of their company's LinkedIn Marketing success rate.

Relationship between demographic variables and LinkedIn marketing:

The purpose of chi-square analysis for this research is to understand that relationship of all the demographic variables with the LinkedIn Marketing. Around five hypotheses were formulated in order to test all the demographic variables will have whether significant relationship with

LinkedIn Marketing or not. Table 1 showing all those hypotheses and its result along with significance value arrived from chi-square analysis.

Table 1: Results from Chi square analysis

Sl. No.	Hypothesis	Significance value	Result
1	H1: There is a relationship between age and awareness of LinkedIn marketing	0.045	H ₀ Rejected
2	H2: There is no relationship between marital status and awareness of LinkedIn marketing	0.224	H ₀ Accepted
3	H3: There is no relationship between income level and awareness of LinkedIn marketing	0.575	H ₀ Accepted
4	H4: There is a relationship between occupation and awareness of LinkedIn marketing	0.026	H ₀ Rejected
5	H5: There is no relationship between industrial sector and awareness of LinkedIn marketing	0.293	H ₀ Accepted

Since the significant value of H1 hypothesis was 0.045 null hypothesis accepted ($p < 0.05$). It shows that there is a relationship between age and awareness of LinkedIn Marketing. In second Hypothesis (H2) the significant value was 0.224 which shows there is no relationship between Marital Status and awareness of LinkedIn Marketing. In third Hypothesis (H3) the significant value is 0.575 which shows there is no relationship between income level and awareness of LinkedIn Marketing. In fourth Hypothesis (H4) the significant value is 0.026 which shows there is a relationship between occupations and awareness of LinkedIn Marketing. In fifth Hypothesis (H5) the significant value is 0.293 which shows there is no relationship between Industrial sector and awareness of LinkedIn Marketing. From the above five hypothesis researcher has identified that two demographic variables such as age and occupation were having significant relationship with the LinkedIn Marketing.

Factors influencing the LinkedIn marketing:

From the review of literature, around five major factors such as marketing tool, marketing strategy, focus, deal closing and belief were identified for determining the factors influencing the LinkedIn marketing. In this regard, regression analysis was carried out by keeping LinkedIn marketing awareness as dependent variable and five other variables as independent variables. Tables 2 and 3 shows the results obtained from regression analysis. Table 2 shows the R² value of 0.254 and significance value of 0.033. It indicates that around 25% of the variance was explained by all these five variables and all the five variables were significant since the significance value of 0.033 ($p < 0.05$). These results were justifying the validity of regression analysis for this research work and hence final results could be considered for declaring the results.

Table 2: Model Summary and ANOVA results of regression analysis

R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	F	Sig.
0.504	0.254	0.134	0.388	3.275	0.033

Table 3 shows the results of significant variables from the regression analysis. Out of all five variables, two variables such as marketing strategy ($P = 0.033$) and ($P = 0.037$) were showing the significance relationship ($P < 0.05$) with awareness on LinkedIn marketing.

Unstandardized coefficients are used to understand the influence of each independent significant variable on the dependent variable of awareness on LinkedIn marketing. For example, every one unit increases in marketing strategy, will increase 0.217 units of awareness on LinkedIn marketing, similarly every one unit changes in belief of respondents for focusing LinkedIn and email marketing will generate leads will influence awareness on LinkedIn marketing 0.247 units positively.

Table 3: Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficient Beta	t.	Sig.
(Constant)	1.022	0.241		4.232	0
LinkedIn Marketing Powerful Business tool for lead generation	0.053	0.128	0.107	0.417	0.679
Organisation follow LinkedIn Marketing Strategy	0.217	0.097	0.431	2.228	0.033
organisation focus on LinkedIn respondents' view	-0.082	0.229	-0.089	-0.359	0.722
Does Telemarketing Team closes deal from LinkedIn	0.077	0.085	0.169	0.911	0.369
Believe of Respondents' Company focuses on LinkedIn and email for lead generation	0.247	0.114	0.385	2.178	0.037

Finally, standardized coefficients were used to identify the important variable towards LinkedIn marketing awareness. Based on the regression results, it has been found that marketing strategy (0.431) plays major role followed by belief of respondents (0.385).

CONCLUSION:

From the review of literatures, one could understand that LinkedIn Marketing is playing very vital position in B2B business for lead generation and to generate revenue. This research concludes that demographic factors like age and occupation are having strong influence on the awareness of LinkedIn marketing. Further, this research reveals that marketing strategy plays a major role followed by belief of respondents. Hence it is suggested that digital marketing strategist could prefer to do marketing through LinkedIn marketing strategies and belief based attitude and values for getting big projects from the client. This also helps to have proper coordination between digital marketing strategist and offline marketing team which will help to deal B2B projects smoothly. From the various literature researcher has observed that there is a connection between LinkedIn, email marketing, content writing which pushes the business further to close the deal and generate revenue to the company.

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